

STUDIES IN LONG-CHAIN ACIDS. PART VI. ON ALEURITIC ACID

BY P. C. MITTER, MUNINDRA CHANDRA SEN-GUPTA AND AMALENDU BOSE

A geometrical isomer of aleuritic acid has been obtained while attempting the synthesis of aleuritic acid.

Mitter and Mukherji (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 303) have synthesised ω -methoxy- Δ^9 -hexadecenoic acid which is an intermediate product in their intended synthesis of aleuritic acid. The work has now been extended by the present workers leading to the synthesis of a geometrical isomer of aleuritic acid, according to the following scheme:—

It was originally proposed to convert the methoxy ester (I) into the corresponding bromo-acid by treatment with hydrobromic acid. The procedure led, however, to extensive decomposition of the methoxy ester. The replacement of the OMe by chlorine could be conveniently effected by heating with hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19) in a sealed tube. The chloro acid (II), obtained in an excellent yield, was esterified and converted into the acetoxy ester (IV) by treatment with potassium acetate in glacial acetic acid. The acetoxy ester (IV) could be converted into the corresponding dihydroxy compound (V) by oxidation with perhydrol in glacial acetic acid solution. Hydrolysis with alcoholic potash gave a geometrical isomer of aleuritic acid (VI).

The acid, obtained by this method, was found to melt at 125° after two crystallisations from ethyl acetate, while the acid obtained from natural sources melts at 101°. A mixture of the two acids melted also at 101°. The natural acid forms an acetone compound and therefore it possesses the two contiguous OH groups in *cis*-configuration. The synthetic acid is therefore presumably the *trans*-variety. Attempts at its conversion into the *cis*-form are in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl 16-Chloro- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate (III).—The methoxy ester (I) (2.5 g.) with 3 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 10 c.c. of fuming hydrochloric acid, was heated in a glass tube in a bomb-furnace at 160–80° for 6 hours. After cooling, the product was poured into cold water, extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether distilled off. As the free acid could not be obtained in a sufficiently pure condition for analysis it was esterified with absolute alcohol and sulphuric acid in the usual way, poured into ice-water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, then with water, dried and the ether removed. The residue distilled at 184°/5 mm. (Found: C, 68.5; H, 10.5; Cl, 10.6. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{33}\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$ requires C, 68.2; H, 10.4; Cl, 11.2 per cent).

Ethyl 16-Acetoxy- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate (IV).—A mixture of the dry chloro-ester (3.6 g.), fused potassium acetate (4 g.) and glacial acetic acid (14 c.c.) was refluxed on an oil-bath at 120–130° for 40 hours. A crystal of sodium iodide was added to the reaction mixture. On the completion of the reaction the product was poured into ice-water, extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water and finally dried over calcium chloride. After removal of the ether, the residue

distilled at $185-90^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 2 g. (Found : C, 70'9 ; H, 10'3. $C_{26}H_{36}O_4$ requires C, 70'6 ; H, 10'6 per cent).

Ethyl 16-Acetoxy-9 : 10-dihydroxyhexadecoate (V).—Perhydrol (9'4 g.) was taken in glacial acetic acid (34 g.) distilled over chromic acid and heated for one hour at 80° . After cooling the mixture to room temperature the acetoxy ester (4'5 g.) was added and the mixture shaken. The temperature of the mixture rose rapidly without the application of heat reaching a maximum of 70° . After cooling to room temperature, it was allowed to stand overnight. Acetic acid was next removed by steam distillation and the residue cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed and then dried with calcium chloride. On removal of the ether, a pale yellow viscous liquid remained which was presumably the desired compound (V). As it could not be obtained sufficiently pure for analysis, it was hydrolysed to the free acid.

$\omega : 9 : 10$ -*Trihydroxyhexadecoic acid* (VI).—The above acetoxy ester (3 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic caustic soda (3 g. NaOH in 30 c.c. alcohol) for 6 hours. The alcohol was then removed by heating on the water-bath with the addition of successive small amounts of water. The solution was then cooled with ice and acidified with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid. The acid separated as a pale yellow coloured solid. It was filtered, washed and dried. It was purified by two crystallisations from ethylacetate. The final product was colourless. It did not decolourise bromine. The melting point was found to be 125° and it did not rise on further crystallisation. The mixed m. p. with natural aleuritic acid was found to be 101° . (Found : C, 63'28 ; H, 10'45. $C_{16}H_{22}O_8$ requires C, 63'15 ; H, 10'52 per cent).

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received July 18, 1944.